

DryCake

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Vertical Separator with Mechanical Dewatering and Thermomechanical Surface Cleaning: Functional Disclosure

Technical Note — Marc Vanderbeken, inventor — Published April 2026

PURPOSE OF THIS DISCLOSURE

This document constitutes a public technical disclosure establishing prior art for the functional capabilities described herein. It is published in the public domain to prevent third-party patenting of the described results and applications. It does not disclose the specific mechanical implementation, which is the subject of patent applications pending in multiple jurisdictions.

TECHNOLOGY: TWISTER VERTICAL SEPARATOR

The Twister is a vertical axis separator developed by DryCake (De Panne, Belgium) that processes wet, contaminated heterogeneous waste streams and delivers two separated output fractions in a single continuous pass, without thermal drying and without chemical washing.

OUTPUT FRACTIONS

Top discharge:

Dry, surface-cleaned plastics and films. Liquid moisture mechanically removed. Colloidal surface contamination including greases and oils substantially reduced. No downstream thermal dryer required.

Bottom discharge:

Dewatered organic materials. Moisture depleted by mechanical action. No phase change. No heating to boiling point required.

KEY PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS

- Moisture reduction achieved mechanically, ejected as liquid — not as vapor — requiring no phase change and no energy input for evaporation.
- Surface cleaning of plastic film achieved without chemical washing agents.
- Three-way separation of mixed waste streams: resilient materials (metals, stones), low-density materials (plastics, films), and moisture-laden organics — all within a single apparatus.
- Single continuous upward airflow separates fractions by differential material response, not by density sorting alone.
- Thermomechanical surface cleaning effect: at elevated internal temperatures, colloidal contaminants adhering to plastic surfaces detach under mechanical action. Heated air at 40-90 degrees C introduced into the processing zone reduces contaminant viscosity, allowing detachment under vane impact. Contaminants sink to bottom discharge while cleaned plastics exit at top.
- Inherent thermal safety: the highest temperature zone coincides with the highest moisture content zone, eliminating fire risk present in conventional dryers where the hottest zone coincides with the driest material.
- Kinetic energy from rotating vanes converts partly to heat through friction and impact, raising internal processing zone temperature by approximately 5-10 degrees C independently of any external heat

source.

- Continuous operation, no batch cycle.

DEMONSTRATED APPLICATIONS

- Post-depackaging wet organic/plastic mixed streams (municipal solid waste, food waste)
 - Wet source-separated organics with plastic film contamination
 - Paper mill pulper rejects (LC and FFD fractions) — moisture reduction from 61-75% to 26%
 - Wet RDF (Refuse Derived Fuel) preparation
 - Wholesale market organic waste streams with fibrous and plastic contamination
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PATENT STATUS

The mechanical implementation of the above-described functions is the subject of granted patents and pending patent applications in the United States, Europe (Unitary Patent), and other jurisdictions, in the name of Marc Vanderbeken and/or DryCake. This disclosure covers functional results and application areas only. All patent rights reserved.

INVENTOR DECLARATION

I, Marc Vanderbeken, Belgian national, inventor and founder of DryCake, De Panne, Belgium, hereby publish this technical disclosure on April 19, 2026, for the purpose of establishing public prior art. The technology described herein has been developed by me and my co-inventors Cedric Vanderbeken and Olivier Vanderbeken.

/Marc Vanderbeken/

Marc Vanderbeken — April 19, 2026